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The Development of Number Space Mapping on Three Axes

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Abstract

Accurate number line representations reliably predict children's future arithmetic performance [1]. There is substantial evidence linking the semantic representation of numbers to the physical properties of external space [2,3,4]. The most influential support for this connection comes from the SNARC effect (Spatial Numerical Association of Response Codes), where small/large numbers are responded to faster on the left/right side of space. Extensively replicated, this demonstrates horizontal mapping of numerical magnitude. Much less is known about how numbers are represented on the vertical axis and sagittal plane and how spatial numerical associations on multiple axes develop in childhood [5,6,]. In a 2AFC within subject's paradigm, children, aged 6-10, and adults performed a single digit magnitude comparison task with response buttons positioned up/down (vertical), left/right (horizontal) and near/far (sagittal). Results show that number-space mapping by axis changes across development. At the beginning of formal education (age 6) children show a SNARC effect that is not biased by any axis. By third class, (age 9) the vertical axis emerges as most salient, persisting through to adulthood where both horizontal and vertical number-space mappings are most prominent. Findings from this study directly inform the design of assistive educational technology for both blind and sighted children.

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References

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